

Review

Morgenthau's Balance of Power: A Study of Sino-US Assistance in Myanmar

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Abstract: This study analyzes Sino-US competitiveness in Myanmar using Hans Morgenthau's balance of power theory. Myanmar is strategically located in the Indo-Pacific region and is a focus area for US-China. Each power has used strategic assistance to influence Myanmar, with the US emphasizing democratic governance, human rights, and sanctions and China focusing on infrastructure development, economic investments, and political alliances, particularly through its Belt and Road Initiative. This study examines how both countries use these techniques to counteract each other's growth and avoid regional hegemony. This research contends that Morgenthau's balance of power theory, wherein nations are motivated by the desire to survive and avoid domination by a single power, is still relevant to international politics. The US and China use economic, political, and military assistance methods to defend their interests in Myanmar without each other winning. Nevertheless, Myanmar has adopted and practiced an independent and non-aligned foreign policy, attempting to avoid being drawn too closely into the sphere of influence of either China or the US. This analysis found that Myanmar's location between South and East Asia and access to major commercial routes and resources made it a significant theater for Sino-U.S. competition. The research shows how smaller governments like Myanmar might profit from strong power rivalry while preserving autonomy. Further study indicates that Myanmar's internal political dynamics and foreign effects are complicated and that the region's power balance affects regional stability and global politics.

Keywords: Balance of Power, Sino-US Competition, Strategic Assistance, Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), Regional Stability.

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Introduction

The ongoing political rivalry between China and the United States can be seen clearly in their competition for influence in Myanmar. Both countries are keen to assert their presence and pursue their national interests through cooperation and strategic interactions. External factors, such as China and the US, see Myanmar as a crucial platform for advancing their economic goals. Myanmar, in response, has adopted a foreign policy centered on balancing external influence with maintaining its internal sovereignty. By engaging in economic diplomacy, working with regional organizations like Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), and fostering non-aligned relationships with both China and the US, Myanmar has effectively navigated the Sino-US rivalry while safeguarding its national interests. This strategy allows Myanmar to play a pivotal role in regional affairs. While China has focused on economic development and

infrastructure support, the US has prioritized democratic governance, human rights, and civil freedoms, each vying for influence in Myanmar's development. The balance of power theory offers further insight into how nations collaborate to prevent any single power from achieving dominance, which is essential in understanding the dynamics of this rivalry.

Background of Sino-US Assistance in Myanmar

Myanmar is a strategically important nation for international powers, particularly China and the US, since it borders China, India, Thailand, and Bangladesh and has a coastline in the Bay of Bengal and the Andaman Sea (Sun, 2021). Myanmar has experienced periods of civil unrest and political change, which impacted its political engagement with the international community. However, in 2011, the country-initiated steps toward democratic reform. The two global superpowers, China and the United States began to deepen their economic and political ties with Myanmar as the country gradually opened up to the outside world. As a result, the US saw an opportunity for constructive engagement with its larger strategic objectives in Southeast Asia with Myanmar's shift from a military rule to a model of a quasi-democratic society (Kipgen, 2019). At first, support for these changes came in the form of assistance and encouragement for American investors, as well as a dollar-easing of certain economic penalties. Aside from the previous over-reliance on China, Myanmar's neighbor, the US assistance was primarily intended to help civil society, democratic institutions, and economic progress (Haacke, 2021).

China has been Myanmar's largest trade partner and major investor since the 1980s, particularly in the fields of infrastructure, energy, and the exploitation of natural resources (Maung, 2022). Taking into account its strategic circle and its economic and security interests in Myanmar, the PRC has both strategic and economic stakes in the region. From an economic perspective, Myanmar has substantial mineral, gas, and oil resources that provide a "life-line" for China's energy needs. Via the China-Myanmar Economic Corridor (CMEC), a key element of the Chinese government's BRI project, Myanmar may act as a gateway to the Indian Ocean. As a result, China may use this overland route to circumvent the clogged Malacca Strait and will not be affected by closures during South China Sea conflicts (Yu, 2021).

China, in contrast to the US, has not given much thought to democratizing Myanmar or advocating for the defense of freedoms and human rights, even as it supports the efforts of Myanmar's Junta to maintain the two nations' economic ties in spite of a repressive regime. China refrained from opposing the policy change in Myanmar in February 2021, citing the need to protect its commercial interests and maintain regional peace (Maung, 2022). This is consistent with China's strategy in Southeast Asia, wherein the nation seeks to uphold regimes that share its interests by endorsing officials of any political inclination (Yu, 2021).

Thus, another facet of the continuing power struggle in Myanmar is best shown by the positions of the US and China. The US sees Myanmar as a site where it can establish itself, promote democracy, and defend its own interests in the ongoing struggle against China's increasing power in the Indo-Pacific area. The US seeks to undermine China's strategic clout in Myanmar by concentrating on the country's economic development and therefore endorsing democratic institutions (Haacke, 2021). But the US has a big job ahead of it in this area, particularly considering the complex networks China has had to establish over the years via strategic political influence and economic prosperity with both military and civilian players in Myanmar (Sun, 2021).

Myanmar and China are called 'Pauk-phauw' (Brothers) friendship, it reflects the close relationship between Myanmar and China. China's relationship with Myanmar is not without difficulties, just like any other foreign partnership. China has long been a crucial actor in Myanmar, with bilateral relations greatly influenced by economic interconnectivity projects, particularly in relation to the Belt and Road initiatives. The influence of the U.S. "Indo-Pacific Strategy" on China's neighborly diplomacy, Myanmar has become a channel for China's "Belt and Road" initiative and the expansion of China's resource imports. It is an important support for China's participation in Southeast Asia and South Asia in its open economic development (Liao Chunyong, Zhao Han, 2022). However, Myanmar's policy towards China has undergone significant changes due to political unrest, political factors, and Western opinions, and relations between

the two countries leading to a series of ups and downs (Pan Dani, 2022). The policy changes in Myanmar have created political unrest, undermining China's capacity to maintain the stability necessary to undertake long-term strategic investments (Maung, 2022).

The US-China rivalry that is now evident in Myanmar is quite representative of the larger competition that is taking place across Southeast Asia. As a result, both countries are attempting to realize their larger diplomatic goals in the area of southeast Asia by using their strategic support for Myanmar. As a result, Myanmar is always caught up in the Sino-US rivalry, attempting to direct both countries' influence to achieve development and sovereignty (Sun, 2021; Kipgen, 2019).

However, Myanmar's foreign policy has sought to avoid being drawn too closely into the sphere of influence of China or the United States. This position would allow Myanmar to benefit from both powers and maintain a level of autonomy. For example, Myanmar is engaging with China for economic benefits and infrastructure development, especially in areas such as democratic governance and human rights, while cooperating with the United States to improve its international image.

Hans Morgenthau's Theory of Balance of Power

Prominent political realist Hans Morgenthau asserts that there is no universal police force or ultimate authority to regulate state behavior, making the international system as a whole anarchic (Morgenthau, 1948). With this kind of organization, nations must acquire authority as they are on their own in a self-help system with no outside support. According to Morgenthau (1978), the balance is a mechanism that keeps things in an equilibrium condition such that no state, or even a coalition of states, could take control of it.

Naturally, the key tenet of Morgenthau's theory is that the balance of power shapes international politics structurally rather than being a choice (Waltz, 1979). According to this viewpoint, governments are compelled to engage in power-balancing measures like forming alliances, building their armed forces, or engaging in diplomacy. These are actions made in response to other states' threats and to ensure that the non-state actor cannot become the dominant force in the international system (Lobell, 2020).

Morgenthau also highlights the rationale that underlies governmental decision-making, particularly in the area of foreign policy. These choices are based on an approximation of how the current international environment may be altered to preserve or enhance their power strengths in the international system's power configuration (Morgenthau, 1948). According to Morgenthau, this logical calculation always determines state behavior, leaving the balance of power largely up to chance as states constantly modify their strategies to maintain the equilibrium of power within the international system (Schweller, 2016).

Purpose of the Study

This research examined the struggle between the United States and China in Myanmar by analyzing the applications of Morgenthau's balance of power method. In this instance, the research used a strategic assistance analysis to demonstrate how each of the two powers made sure the other did not control the other in the area. In particular, the research demonstrated that the US and China are appropriate for Morgenthau by examining how their respective behaviors differ and adhere to the principles of power balance. The goal was to demonstrate how Myanmar's position between these two superpowers made it a vital battleground for maintaining stability across South-East Asia and the wider globe.

II. Theoretical Framework: Morgenthau's Balance of Power

Overview of Balance of Power

One of the most important theories in political realism and international affairs today is Hans Morgenthau's balance of power theory. According to Morgenthau, the balance of power in international politics is a real and persistent reality rather than just a logical scientific premise (Morgenthau, 1948). This is the theory that states should have equal power distribution so that no state or group of states can impose its will on another. Power may be distributed in a variety of ways, such as bipolarity, which distributes power between two leading states or two blocks of states, or multipolarity, which distributes power among several states or multiple groups of states (Schweller, 2016).

These are the following mechanisms of the balance of power according to Morgenthau. First, the formation of an alliance system is a reaction to the expansion of a single state or a collection of nations. Second, governments use weaponry, or the development or augmentation of their military might, as a deterrent to other states' attacks. Third, implement counterbalancing measures. According to Waltz (1979), governments alter their foreign policy in order to counter any state that seems to be gaining a dominating influence. These processes demonstrate that conduct aimed at increasing power cannot be attributed to fundamental hostility; rather, it is a response to the structural features of the anarchic international system, where security is equated with power (Lobell 2020). Decentralization of power is aided by the dynamic of states defending and readjusting one another to prevent anyone from overtaking the others.

Application to Contemporary Geopolitics

In today's international politics, Morgenthau's theory of the balance of power is still relevant, particularly when examining the US-China relationship. The South East Asia region is one of the many areas in which these two nations are engaged in a strategic competition. It is difficult to analyze the Sino-US rivalry in the context of Myanmar as a microcosm of the conflicts between the superpowers over how to use their respective military, diplomatic, and economic might to restrain and offset one another's ambitions to rule the Asia-Pacific area (Sun, 2021).

The power-balancing behavior of the Threat/Counter-threat Community in Myanmar is evident when the US and China provide strategic assistance that aligns with their respective, wider regional frameworks. In order to counter China's hegemony, which has established strongholds in political allegiances and infrastructure funding primarily via China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), the US upholds democracy, human rights, and economic prosperity (Maung: 2022). On the other hand, Myanmar attempts to counterbalance the hegemonic power by reducing its reliance on the economy and ensuring the development of its strategic goals via diplomatic ties with its elites, even in the face of shifting political circumstances (Kipgen, 2019). This rivalry also reflects the compromises that China and India make in the Indo-Pacific conflict, as they each want to prevent the other from surpassing them (Haacke, 2021).

Morgenthau's concept of the balance of power can be used to explain the tactics and conflicts that the US and China are experiencing in Myanmar. In order to prevent one another from controlling a vital area of the international system, the two governments take part in actions that preserve the balance of power. The reason Morgenthau's theory still holds true to describe state actions in contemporary international politics is the ongoing shifting of power relations and balances.

III. Historical Context of Sino-US Relations in Myanmar

Myanmar's Strategic Importance

China views Myanmar as strategically significant due to its access to the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and the China-Myanmar Economic Corridor (CMEC) via Myanmar. Linking China's Yunnan province to the western coast of

Myanmar, the CMEC offers several benefits to China. Firstly, it helps the government secure essential energy and air, so increasing the depth of its strategy (Steinberg & Fan, 2020).

It was explained that Myanmar is a key component of the United States' Indo-Pacific strategy, which was created to uphold the idea of an Asia that is "free and open" in order to support China. Because of this, the US can weaken China's influence in the area and disrupt its supply chain because of Myanmar's position. In the larger scheme of preserving regional balance and containing China's increasing dominance, the US views Myanmar as a strategic asset (Haacke, 2021). Due to its location, Myanmar has thus emerged as one of the main areas of conflict between Beijing and Washington, where both parties impose pressure on one another on a political, economic, and even military level.

US Assistance in Myanmar

In the past, US assistance to Myanmar has been justified on the grounds that it promotes democracy, human rights, and political and economic transformation. The United States has increased its involvement with Myanmar since 2011, when the country began a slow process of political change that saw it transition from a military junta to a government that was akin to civil society. This was seen as an opportunity to use tools based on Western democracy to introduce democracy to Myanmar and encourage the nation to join the global community (Pedersen, 2014).

The US was forced to use the following unconventional strategies in order to achieve its goal: diplomatic, economic, and humanitarian. One of the key instruments used was the imposition of sanctions, which put special emphasis on the junta-affiliated businesses and the military in Myanmar. However, massive assistance programs that aimed to support democratic institutions, civil society, economic liberalization, and development were combined with these punitive measures. These initiatives were designed to decrease Myanmar's dependency on China, transition to alternative growth models, and reorient Myanmar's political and economic systems to align with the values of Western democracies. By supporting the process of governance and market reforms that would naturally situate Myanmar in the camp of the United States and like-minded nations, the United States saw in Myanmar's democratization a chance to restrain China's expanding influence in Southeast Asia (Arase, 2020).

China Assistance in Myanmar

Economic, financial, diplomatic, education, and infrastructure assistance for Myanmar may be considered the main aspects of China-Myanmar relations. China's Belt and Road Initiative has found a suitable partner in Myanmar due to the development of many large-scale projects, such as the pipelines carrying gas and oil from Myanmar's western coast to China's Yunnan region. Additionally, China has made investments in the building of deep-sea ports, special economic zones, and trains. Among them is Kyaukphyu Port, which gives the Chinese crucial access to the Indian Ocean (Kipgen, 2019).

Due to its political ties, China has provided political shelter and assistance to Myanmar's ruling class, particularly the military government, during the times when these organizations were cut off from the outside world both politically and economically. For instance, China defended Myanmar in the UN during the Rohingya refugee crisis, when the West was characterizing Myanmar as a pariah state. And then, China has vetoed sanctions imposed on Myanmar at the UN Security Council. China calls for political solution to Rohingya issue, saying "unilateral accusations and pressure" does not work, which also mean it is to show Myanmar that who are Myanmar's true friends. China's actions were routine, and it did not impose any restrictions on human rights on Myanmar. With Myanmar adhering to Chinese strategic policies, China has been able to invest extensively and efficiently thanks to this political backing (Steinberg & Fan, 2020). The policies reflect a positive view of China and the relationship. It has been further developed through the interaction between the two countries. Despite the divergent voices within the government, the Myanmar government's policy towards China still reflects hope for closer ties between Sino-Myanmar relations, and progress is being made in the process of clearing up doubts and ambiguities between the two countries (He Yuxian, 2022).

IV. Applying Morgenthau's Balance of Power to Sino-US Assistance in Myanmar

Competition and Cooperation

The Balance of Power analysis on Sino-US Relations in Myanmar reflects more of Morgenthau's paradigm. One of the most significant countries for both China and the United States is Myanmar. Both nations utilize Myanmar's primary aid tactics to further their own objectives while simultaneously attempting to limit each other's influence.

Thus, by promoting changes to the political system and human rights, the United States seeks to restrain China's growing capabilities in Myanmar, in line with Morgenthau's theory of power balance. Consequently, the US hopes to lessen China's influence in Myanmar and strengthen this nation's adherence to Western ideals via promoting democratic and civil society cultures as well as economic liberalization. As we will see later in Morgenthau's thinking, this strategy is strongly related to the idea that governments desire power in order to prevent competing nations from controlling their authority.

However, China's strategic support is primarily seen as a means of bolstering its political and economic advantages via large investments in infrastructure, particularly in the CMEC, pipelines, and ports sectors. These projects help China's political ties with the military rule in Myanmar in addition to improving China's physical access to the Indian Ocean (Steinberg & Fan, 2020). According to Morgenthau, China is making an effort to maintain its strategic dominance and limit the impact of other nations, particularly the US.

As both countries vie for Myanmar's loyalty, Myanmar emerges victorious and acts as a buffer between them. By strategically positioning itself between the US and China, Myanmar leverages the rivalry and tension to its advantage and advances economically and socially without succumbing to the dominance of any nation. This perspective is consistent with Morgenthau's theory that minorities may influence the competition between superpowers and counteract their influence without coming under their authority (Arase, 2020).

Power Shifts and Stability

It is evident that there is a chance that the US-China relationship and the one with Myanmar would either lead to stability or turmoil in the area. The global political environment between the two superpowers serves as an example of how the conflict system that serves as the foundation for Morgenthau's theory may also guarantee a comparatively stable state of affairs. As a result of the US and China's struggle, there is no hegemonic power control over Myanmar; as a result, sovereignty is maintained (Haacke, 2021).

However, this power dynamics also introduces some instability into the structures. Because foreign pressures have the potential to either enhance or weaken some groups, the ongoing confrontation between the US and China may also contribute to a temptation to intervene in domestic events in Myanmar. For example, China has supported the Myanmar military administration, particularly during the times when the world community strongly denounced it for how it was treating the Rohingya refugees (Kipgen, 2019). However, the United States backing of causes like human rights and democracy may enrage pro-military factions and escalate hostilities.

Because of the unbalanced power, future developments in Sino-US relations might have an impact on Myanmar's domestic politics. As a result, changes in competitiveness and the two powers' shifting priorities have an impact on Myanmar's stability, either via increased rivalry or through the checks and balances of the market (Sun, 2021). As a result, Morgenthau's theories that international politics is a theater of balancing and rebalancing as governments adjust to shifts in power balances are supported by the distribution of power in Myanmar.

V. Challenges to the Balance of Power in Myanmar

Regional Instability and International Responses

In Myanmar, civil unrest is still a significant problem. It is characterized by many civil conflicts between ethnic groups and the military administration, which contribute to regional instability. Because of this, the dynamics of the area are uncertain as both China and the US attempt to apply pressure for the advancement of their respective strategic goals. These have shown China's active involvement in Myanmar in order to maintain its influence and control over regional instability. China has shielded Myanmar from United Nations sanctions and offered its rhetorical and material support in dealing with the so-called terrorist attacks. With Myanmar as a key partner, China has profited from the development of regional infrastructure. Chinese companies have built extensive infrastructure, such as the China-Myanmar Economic Corridor (CMEC), which facilitates commerce and the flow of resources (Steinberg & Fan, 2020). In order to protect its interests in light of instability, China has collaborated with ethnic militias in northern Myanmar, such as the United Wa State Army (UWSA), in addition to its economic investments (Kipgen, 2019). In order to lessen any risks to its strategic interests, China also seeks to guarantee the security of its investments made in these dangerous regions. On the other hand, the United States advocates for democracy and human rights via diplomatic pressure, the International Court, and other venues. For example, the United Nations and other international organizations have been used by the US to put pressure on the government of Myanmar to address the Rohingya crisis and other violations of human rights (Pedersen, 2014). This is consistent with the international pressure that is a component of the US's foreign policy objective to uphold democratic values and, concurrently, diminish China's influence by endorsing Myanmar's democracy. However, since Myanmar's politics are complex and heavily influenced by the military, these initiatives are not particularly effective.

This analogy of these acts only emphasizes what is often thought of as a confrontational balance of power. The US and China are dealing with some complicated circumstances, and uncertainty has the potential to be both a danger and an opportunity. Each power attempts to adjust its strategies to leverage the regional instability to its advantage while mitigating potential risks to its interests (Arase, 2020). This strategic maneuvering underscores the balance of power dynamics described by Morgenthau, where states respond to shifts in regional stability to maintain or enhance their influence.

Impact of Domestic Politics

They also made it apparent that the power dynamics. The military's power influenced, the ongoing ethnic and political unrest, and the controversy surrounding the Rohingya crisis influence how both governments approach their policies in the nation.

China has become a peripheral player in Myanmar's peace process and domestic affairs in general. China supports Myanmar's efforts towards a political reconciliation within the constitutional framework. China has set aside its stated adherence to the principle of non-interference in other countries' internal affairs but has become assertively involved in Myanmar's peace process. It sought to engage directly with the main conflict issues facing Myanmar and to shape the decisions and choices of various players in Myanmar. It has offered to mediate in the conflict and pressured non-signatories along its border to attend a series of Union-level dialogues. China has become a major source of influence over Myanmar due to the continuing friction between the central authorities and the border population. This leverage gives China a means to block or reduce the influence of the United States in Myanmar and, by extension, in the broader Southeast Asian region (USIP, 2018). Although the political changes in Myanmar have not shaken the mutual trust between the two countries, the emphasis is on "brotherly love" at this crucial moment (Liu Jinping, 2022).

Although democratic and human rights policies align with American principles, they face obstacles due to the military's assertiveness. Due to the military's stronghold in the administration, the US has attempted to exert diplomatic and economic pressure on the government of Myanmar, but these efforts have not been particularly successful (Pedersen, 2014). The US must so consider how to encourage the yearning for change while still being sensitive to the political realities in Myanmar. The idea behind the balance of power plan is to overcome political barriers in Myanmar while balancing a strategic change to align with regional aims and objectives (Arase, 2020). Thus, the internal politics of Myanmar have a significant impact on China's and the US's balance of power policies. To accomplish their overall strategic aims and objectives, these great powers must modify their tactics in response to difficulties both domestically and globally and in light of shifting political landscapes (Sun, 2021). They continue the process of adjustment that, as Morgenthau noted, is typical of a system of balance of power; nations respond to changes that occur both at home and abroad.

VI. Conclusion

Summary of Findings

The power dynamics in addressing the situation in Myanmar is better understood by using Hans Morgenthau's balance of power theory. Theoretically, both powers work together to prevent any one of them from gaining hegemony over the other in the area. In the fight against China's hegemony in the area, the US emphasizes the need for political, civil, and economic reforms. This strategy supports Morgenthau's premise that nations want to become more powerful in comparison to one another and weaken their adversaries.

In the 21st century, China and the US have similar aid distribution methods and use multilateral organizations to provide aid. The US's assistance had become a choice because it wanted to reduce overdependence on China which was a dangerous factor for the country's stability and internal welfare. However, for US assistance, the countries require political conditions, China's assistance does not need them and regards itself as a partner, rather than a donor. Apart from the political support required to safeguard its economic interests and secure a kind of safety net from the West, China prioritizes big, substantial infrastructure expenditures. China's involvement in Myanmar provides compelling evidence to Morgenthau's contention that nations use various groups as checks and balances to guarantee their security. One may observe how smaller nations might profit from rival large powers without being absorbed by them by looking at the example in this case, which served as the scene of the rivalry. This article has shown that, using the US and China as contemporary examples, the balance of power paradigm is helpful in understanding how nations' strategic behavior effects Myanmar's growth.

Implications for Future Policy

In the future, Myanmar is probably going to continue serving as an operational theater in the larger Indo-Pacific region's power struggle. However, based on this article they could modify some of these tactics. Changes in the political landscape of Myanmar, for example, may have an impact on how each power responds to such an act.

Therefore, it is crucial for policymakers to comprehend the dynamics of the balance of power with respect to Myanmar in order to facilitate the development of successful foreign policies. Thus, it becomes critical to comprehend the regional security environment when US policy entails competing with another superpower, in this case, China. It is suggested that for long-term stability and to support a balanced order in the area, Myanmar requires effective policies that can strike a balance between great power politics and local political players.

The consolidation of power inside Myanmar will ultimately play a significant role in Sino-American ties and have a profound effect on regional security as well as the stability of the global order. Thus, another layer of new geometrical linkages is anticipated in the conflict between the two countries, and changes in the balance of power will impact both

the containment rules and security. It follows that in order for policymakers' actions to be suitable for both the regional and global realities, they need to be aware of these processes.

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